

Thermo-Chemical Recycling of Polypropylene via High-Power Microwave Plasma Gasification: Syngas and Metal Carbide Production

Jafar Fathi^{a,b,c}, Michal Hlína^a, Tomáš Mates^g, Maksym Buryi^a, Vineet Singh Sikarwar^{a,d}, Radek Mušálek^a, Shelja Sharma^a, Michal Lojka^b, Adéla Jiríčková^b, Ondřej Jankovský^b, Jan Riedl^e, Miroslav Karlík^f, Petr Kratochvíl^e, Hana Thürlová^e, František Růžička^e, Filip Průša^e, Alan Mašláni^{a,*}

^a Institute of Plasma Physics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Za Slovankou 1782/3 182 00, Prague 8, Czech Republic

^b University of Chemistry and Technology, Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

^c Department of Environmental Geosciences, Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Kamýcká 129, Suchbátka 165 00, Prague, Czech Republic

^d University of Chemistry and Technology, Department of Power Engineering, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

^e University of Chemistry and Technology, Department of Metals and Corrosion Engineering, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague 6, Czech Republic

^f Czech Technical University in Prague, Faculty of Nuclear Sciences and Physical Engineering, Trojanova 13, 120 00 Prague 2, Czechia

^g Institute of Physics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Cukrovarnická 10/112, 162 00, Prague 6, Czech Republic

* Corresponding author: maslani@ipp.cas.cz

keywords:

Microwave Plasma; Thermo-Chemical Recycling; Carbon Nanomaterial; Metal Carbide; Mechanical Alloying; Phase Composition;

Abstract.

Difficult waste streams such as polypropylene are a nuisance vis-a-vis its disposal and treatment, and they pose risks to humans and the environment. This study investigates the gasification of polypropylene (PP) polymer granules using a high-power 100 kW microwave plasma system, integrated with a high-temperature reactor. A dried air flow rate of 1000 standard liters per minute (SLM) was supplied to the microwave plasma torch, with oxygen molecules as oxidizing agents during the gasification process. Complete conversion of Polypropylene (PP) into syngas and carbon nanomaterials was achieved. The experiments were conducted with varying PP feed rates, ranging from 5 to 18 kg/h, and the output gas was analyzed under different conditions. The produced carbon nanomaterials were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), X-ray energy-dispersive (EDS), selected area electron diffraction (SAED), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area analysis, laser diffraction (LD) particle size distribution, and Raman spectroscopy. Additionally, synthesized nanomaterials were explored for applications in metal carbide synthesis throughout mechanical alloying. It was found that utilizing nanostructured carbon resulted in the formation of carbides within the powder mixture after just 2 h, with their content further increasing over time. The results highlight the potential of microwave plasma technology for an efficient valorization of a difficult waste stream to produce usable energy and value-added products that contribute to the development of a circular economy.

1. Introduction.

The growing global concern about diverse difficult waste streams such as sewage sludge, plastic waste, medical waste, etc. and their impact on humans, environment, and climate has prompted significant research into sustainable methods for their disposal and valorization [1]. Polypropylene (PP), one of the most widely used thermoplastic polymers, is a major contributor to the plastic waste crisis due to its extensive application in packaging, textiles, and various consumer goods. The non-biodegradable nature of PP, coupled with its accumulation in landfills and oceans, has led to environmental hazards, including pollution and the release of harmful microplastics [2][3]. Moreover, the conventional methods of plastic waste management, such as incineration and landfill disposal, not only exacerbate air pollution but also contribute significantly to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, further intensifying climate change [4][5][6]. Additionally, with conventional methods of plastic recycling, over 90% of plastic waste remains unrecycled [7].

To mitigate the environmental and climate impact of plastic waste, alternative, and advanced waste-to-energy technologies are gaining attention [1]. One such approach is chemical recycling, where plastic waste is broken down at the molecular level to produce valuable raw materials that can re-enter the production cycle. In contrast to mechanical recycling, which often results in degraded material quality [8], chemical recycling restores plastics to their basic chemical components, enabling high-quality reuse and contributing to a circular economy. By converting plastic waste into new raw materials, chemical recycling helps reduce reliance on virgin fossil-based feedstocks and closes the loop on plastic production, promoting sustainability [9].

Within this context, plasma plastic gasification—a form of chemical recycling—presents a promising innovation. Thermal plasma-based gasification uses extremely high temperatures generated by microwave or electric arc plasma or RF plasma to break down polymers such as PP into simpler molecules such as syngas (a mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide) and valuable solid carbon materials [10]. This process is highly efficient, producing minimal solid waste or toxic by-products compared to traditional waste treatment methods [11]. The syngas generated can be used as an energy source or as a building block for new chemicals and fuels, while the carbon nanomaterials produced during the process can be used in high-value applications, including catalysis, energy storage, and material synthesis [12][13]. Microwave plasma gasification offers several advantages over conventional methods. The ability to operate at extremely high

temperatures ensures complete breakdown of plastic waste, leading to higher conversion efficiency and lower emissions. Additionally, this process is versatile and can handle mixed or contaminated plastics, which are often difficult to recycle mechanically. By utilizing plastic waste as a resource rather than disposing of it, plasma gasification contributes to both waste reduction and resource recovery, aligning with the goals of a circular economy.

There are numerous theoretical [14][15] and experimental investigations [10][16][17][18][19] to valorize diverse difficult waste streams employing different types of thermal plasmas. A few studies have used microwave plasma (MWP) to process waste streams, including plastic waste. An integrated 1 kW MW assisted valorization of plastic wastes and CO₂ for H₂ and CO production was carried out by Zhang et al. to produce H₂ and solid carbons, followed by the removal of carbon via CO₂ gasification under microwave irradiation [20]. They reported that the carbon conversion and CO₂ conversion reached up to 70% and 53% respectively. In another study of the same authors [21] MW plasma (700 W) was employed to decompose plastics into hydrogen and carbon nanotubes, wherein iron-based catalysts were used as the microwave susceptor and metal tips were utilized to induce plasma discharging. The yield of H₂ with plasma discharging by using Fe/AC-400 catalyst was found to be 300 mmol·g⁻¹H_{plastic} with traces of CH₄, CO and CO₂ while high-value carbon nanotubes were fabricated. The influence of various process parameters such as gasification temperature, equivalence ratio (ER), and microwave power on syngas yields of PP air gasification were studied in a recent investigation [22]. They notice that an increase in MW power from 600 to 1000 W increases syngas content from 78.2 to 84.0 wt.% and then decreased to 68.9 wt.%. Syngas High Heat Value (HHV) and maximum cold gas efficiency were respectively found to be 19.3 MJ/Nm³ and 79.1%.

The microwave plasma gasification process produces valuable syngas; however, the characterization and utilization of the solid carbon byproduct could significantly enhance the process's value. This aspect has not been comprehensively considered in gasification studies, primarily because solid residues from gasification often contain high amounts of tar or unconverted hydrocarbons, which are typically understudied.

However, microwave plasma thermochemical conversion of plastics presents an excellent opportunity to achieve high conversion of hydrocarbons into hydrogen and CO, while also

producing almost pure carbon. Fathi et al. [10] conducted a comprehensive characterization of solid carbon obtained from the steam DC torch plasma gasification of PP. BongJu Lee et al. [23] utilized microwave plasma for plastic waste pyrolysis, effectively eliminating tar using a steam microwave torch. They also applied microwave plasma for methane dry reforming, aiming to reduce soot production. Their findings indicated that the amount of soot generated was negligible [24]. Many studies primarily focus on minimizing soot production and maximizing carbon conversion efficiency. However, this approach may not align perfectly with greenhouse gas (GHG) emission mitigation goals. We believe that pyrolysis and gasification processes should prioritize maximizing hydrogen extraction from hydrocarbons while retaining carbon in solid form. This strategy can significantly improve the carbon footprint of the process by preventing the conversion of carbon into gaseous forms such as carbon dioxide or carbon monoxide, which eventually contribute to GHG emissions. Instead, our approach emphasizes producing tar-free solid carbon, which can then be utilized in various applications, thereby reducing the overall environmental impact [24].

In recent years, high-end metallic materials have become extensively researched, with efforts focused on their further enhancement to achieve unprecedented properties. Promising approaches include microstructural refinement, intensive plastic deformation, and the incorporation of reinforcing particles to create composite materials with superior characteristics. Considering the approaches, particle-reinforced materials might comprise all the benefits arising from the mentioned, according to the chosen preparation technique. In this case, the mechanical alloying/milling not only refines the microstructure but also allows the materials to undergo intensive plastic deformation, while the finely dispersed reinforcing particles might not only hinder the microstructural coarsening at elevated temperatures but also reduce thermal expansion.

Considering the principles of a circular economy and the need to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, thermal plasma processes might also accelerate a potential breakthrough in material-oriented research. This process generates valuable hydrogen and produces nanostructured solid carbon as a by-product. Utilizing the nanostructured carbon by-product can significantly enhance the properties of metallic materials. One notable approach involves the targeted preparation of metal carbides (MeC, where Me represents a transition metal) using the nanostructured precursors. These types of C precursors can improve reinforcing capabilities and accelerate the synthesis process due

to their high specific surface area, which boosts reactivity. Among metal carbides, titanium carbide (TiC) stands out due to its remarkable mechanical properties, achieving one of the highest hardness values among known metal carbides, reaching up to 32 GPa [25][26][27][28][29], a value comparable to molybdenum carbide (Mo_2C , [26][27][29]) and hafnium carbide (HfC) [28] being surpassed only by vanadium carbide (VC), which achieves 33 GPa [25][27][29][30]. TiC also demonstrates Young's modulus of 451 GPa, which, while not the highest among carbides, remains substantial compared to other materials. For instance, tungsten carbide (WC) boasts the highest Young's modulus among carbides at 707 GPa.

Mechanical alloying can be employed to synthesize TiC through several sequential steps. Initially, intensive plastic deformation of titanium increases crystallographic lattice defects, facilitating carbon diffusion into the titanium lattice. As carbon content rises, coarse-grained TiC begins to form. This coarse-grained TiC undergoes fragmentation and refinement during the process, accompanied by significant heating of the milling jar. According to some studies, this refinement can reduce carbide particle size to as small as 2 ± 1 nm [31], although other research reports slightly larger particle sizes of approximately 10 ± 1 nm [32].

Incorporating TiC reinforcing particles into high-end alloys offers a promising approach for significantly enhancing their mechanical properties. However, it is well known that the amount of reinforcement is limited, and exceeding the threshold volume fraction can lead to a decline in these properties. For example, Huang S. et al. [33], reported a decrease in the mechanical properties of a CoCrFeNiMn high-entropy alloy when the content of TiC exceeded 7.5 vol.%. This behavior was attributed to the agglomeration of reinforcing particles, which reduced their ability to effectively transfer load-bearing stresses to the composite matrix.

To maximize the strengthening effect, the fine dispersion of TiC particles within the alloy is critical, as it enhances Orowan dislocation strengthening. Additionally, the introduction of TiC particles has been reported not only to refine the microstructure [34][35] but also to stabilize it during both compaction and subsequent exposure to elevated temperatures. This stabilization occurs due to the pinning of grain boundaries by the particles [36], thereby retaining the fine-grained structure of the alloy. Moreover, TiC additions have been shown to reduce the thermal expansion of such composite alloys [34]. From this perspective, the utilization of TiC particles derived from waste by-products of the thermal plasma process presents a highly cost-effective and

efficient method for obtaining nanostructured reinforcements. This approach holds significant potential, particularly given the substantial benefits these particles offer in terms of both microstructural refinement and enhanced mechanical performance.

The cardinal objective and novelty of the present work is the deployment of a high-power plasma (100 kW) to valorize PP for the production of syngas and carbon nanomaterials. A high-power MW plasma in the order of 100 kW has not been investigated to process plastic waste hitherto (to the best of the authors' knowledge). One example of using a microwave plasma torch of similar power as in this work (40 kW) can be mentioned: Uhm et al. [37] used the steam microwave plasma torch for the gasification of the low-grade coal. Secondly, the produced carbon nanomaterials were characterized using a wide variety of characterization methods including X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), X-ray energy-dispersive (EDS), selected area electron diffraction (SAED), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area analysis, laser diffraction (LD) particle size distribution, and Raman spectroscopy to develop insights. Another significant objective is to assess the suitability of carbon nanomaterials to synthesize metal carbides that are critical for their applications in making cutting tools, wear-resistant materials, and high-temperature technologies. Moreover, an analysis of the energetic efficiency of the presented MW system is carried out along with an assessment to find any possibility for energy recovery. This investigation demonstrates the potential of the MW plasma system as a sustainable solution for plastic waste management along with the production of clean energy and value-added materials and therefore, it can safely be taken as a significant step towards the circular economy.

2. Experiment

2.1 Experimental procedures

A 100 kW maximum electrical input power microwave atmospheric pressure plasma torch manufactured by Muegge GmbH company, operating with air as the working gas and a microwave frequency of 915 MHz, was used in this study. The plasma torch was mounted to the upper part of the PlasGas reactor, shown in **Figure 1**. The same 200 L capacity entrained flow reactor utilized by the DC hybrid Steam Torch for PP gasification by Fathi et al. [10], and the reactor configuration is described in different previous works by Mašláni et al. [16][17][38][39][40] for various experiments with different hydrocarbon sources, such as plasma gasification and pyrolysis. Initially, the reactor was preheated using electric heating elements up to 900 °C, after which the microwave plasma was ignited, set to the maximum power and utilized for further elevation of the reactor temperature to reach the level around 1200 °C. A schematic of the experimental setup is depicted in **Figure 1** and a photo of the system is shown in **Figure 2**. The primary gasification process occurs inside of this high-temperature reactor in the “Plasma-Material Interaction Zone” highlighted in **Figure 1**.

Polypropylene (PP) granules were fed into the reactor through a solid feeding system (Hopper) and the gasification of the PP was studied in different operational conditions and at different feeding rates. For the first **operational mode (OP)**, OP1, microwave plasma power was set to 20 kW and the airflow rate was 933 SLM, while for the rest of the operational modes, the power was set to 40 kW, the airflow rate was fixed to 1016 SLM and the PP feeding rate was varied. In certain conditions, an additional flow of argon was introduced to enable the calibration of the flows, while in others, yet another gas CO₂ was added to investigate its impact, specifically, to evaluate the potential of the CO₂ utilization in the gasification process. The operational conditions of the experiment are summarized in the **Table 1**.

Figure 1. The schematic of the experiment setup includes a Microwave Plasma torch system, Reactor, Hopper, Quenching tower, and solid carbon Filtration system.

Figure 2. General view of a microwave plasma torch installed on a plasma chemical reactor PlasGas.

Table 1. Operation conditions of the experiment

Operation condition number	Microwave power (kW)	PP Feed rate (kg/h)	Input plasma torch feed airflow (SLM)	Input reactor CO₂ (SLM)	Input reactor Ar (SLM)
OP1	20	6	933	0	0
OP2	40	10	1016	0	0
OP3	40	15	1016	0	200
OP4	40	15	1016	0	0
OP5	40	18	1016	0	0
OP6	40	18	1016	0	200
OP7	40	18	1016	46	0
OP8	40	5-10	1016	46	200

For real-time output gas analysis, an Omnistar GSD 301 quadrupole mass spectrometer, employing electron impact ionization, (Pfeiffer Vacuum GmbH, Germany) and FTIR spectrometer MATRIX-MG01 equipped with a 10 cm gas cell (Bruker, USA) were utilized. A sampling line runs from the reactor in the part where the produced syngas leaves it, and two filters together with a freezing unit are placed in the line to prevent damage to the mass spectrometer vacuum pumps.

The carbon-bearing material obtained from the plasma gasification of polypropylene was utilized for the targeted synthesis of titanium carbides via ultrashort-term mechanical alloying (MA). The most stable titanium carbide (TiC) composition was selected as the target, with Ti-to-C atomic ratios of 1:1 and 1:2 to ensure equal and also a higher carbon content in the powder mixture.

The MA process was performed in a milling jar filled with milling balls, both made of AISI 420 stainless steel. Powder batches were prepared by mixing titanium powder (Strem Chemicals, 99% purity having particle size $\approx 44 \mu\text{m}$) with nanostructured carbon in the specified atomic proportions. Two batches of powder, weighing 5 g and 20 g, were prepared for distinct purposes. The 5 g batch was used to pre-clean the milling jar, enhancing the standard cleaning protocol, which includes cleaning with SiC particles, rinsing with water and detergent, and ultrasonic cleaning. This additional step was necessary because AISI 420 stainless steel, despite its hardness

of 58–63 HRC as specified by the manufacturer [41], remains susceptible to imprinting from previously milled materials, which could contaminate subsequent preparations.

The 5 g batches, prepared at Ti:C atomic ratios of 1:1 and 1:2, were used to capture potential contaminants, ensuring more reliable experimental results. The powders were placed into the milling jar along with the milling balls, maintaining a ball-to-powder weight ratio of 60:1 for the cleaning process (15:1 for the 20 g powder batch). To mitigate cold welding of the powder particles to the jar and ball surfaces, 4 wt.% of n-heptane was added. The jar was then sealed and flushed with high-purity argon (99.996%) for at least 2 min at a flow rate of 2 L/min to replace the internal atmosphere more than four times. Finally, the jar was pressurized with argon to prevent oxygen contamination during the mechanical alloying process.

Both the cleaning and mechanical alloying processes were conducted under identical conditions: a milling speed of 400 rpm with 30-min milling segments interspersed with 10-min dwell periods for cooling. The cleaning process lasted 1 h and 10 min. For the mechanical alloying process, the kinetics of phase formation were studied by sampling the powder every 2 h, with the total processing time reaching up to 8 h (10 h and 30 min, including dwell periods).

2.2 Analytical equipment

STEM observations were carried out using a high-resolution scanning electron microscope Apreo 2 S LoVac (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Czechia) and 30 kV acceleration voltage. Samples were dispersed in isopropanol, sonicated and shaken for several minutes. The suspension was dripped on lacey carbon support film on copper mesh and left to dry. Bright field (BF), dark field (DF), and high angle annular dark field (HAADF) modes were used for observation.

For TEM analysis, the powder of carbon nanomaterial was deposited dry on a standard 3 mm copper grid covered by the holey carbon film. After fixation in the TEM single-tilt specimen holder, bigger particles were removed using the vacuum tweezer. The sample was examined using 200 keV electrons first in a JEOL JEM 2000FX and later in a JEOL 2200FS TEM equipped with a field-emission gun and JEOL X-ray energy-dispersive (EDS) detector Centurion.

The specific surface area of the sample was determined using the Brunauer, Emmett, and Teller (BET) method, with a NOVAtouch LX2 sorption analyzer from Anton-Paar Instruments. Before the analysis, the sample underwent a 10-hour desorption process at 50 °C under high vacuum conditions to prevent any degradation or decomposition. The analysis utilized a nitrogen-cooled detector at 77 K, and both the BET and Kelvin equations were applied during data interpretation. A comprehensive 40-point BET measurement was performed on the dry, degassed sample. The pore size distribution was assessed by Density Functional theory analysis, showing the distribution of pore volumes (in cubic centimeters per gram, cc/g) as a function of half pore width (in nanometers, nm).

The particle size distribution was analyzed using the laser diffraction method on a Malvern Panalytical Mastersizer 3000, equipped with a 4 mW He-Ne 632.8 nm red light source and a 10 mW LED 470 nm blue light source. The measurement range was set from 0.01 to 3000 μm . Measurements were conducted in a wet cell with isopropyl alcohol (Penta, purity p.a.) as the dispersant. A constant suspension mixing speed of 3000 rpm was maintained throughout the analysis. Each sample was measured five times (five scans), and the particle size distribution was calculated from the average values.

Raman spectra were obtained using an inVia Raman microscope (Renishaw, England) in backscattering geometry with a CCD detector. A DPSS laser (532 nm, 50 mW) with an applied power of 5 mW and a 50x objective was used for the measurement. Instrument calibration was performed using a silicon reference, with the peak positioned at 520 cm^{-1} and a resolution of less than 1 cm^{-1} . A small amount of powdered sample was placed on a silicon wafer for measurement. Graph deconvolution was conducted using Origin 2022b software.

The chemical and phase compositions of the prepared Ti-C powders were analyzed using X-ray fluorescence (XRF, Thermo ARL 9400 XP) and X-ray diffraction (XRD, PANalytical X'Pert PRO). The XRD analysis employed $\text{CuK}\alpha_1$ (0.15406 nm) and $\text{CuK}\alpha_2$ (0.15443 nm) radiation, with a $\text{K}\alpha_2/\text{K}\alpha_1$ ratio of 0.5.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Produced Syngas characterization

Figure 3 shows the temperature evolution in different parts of the reactor during the experiment. While in the beginning of the experiment (OP1) the temperatures in the reactor were relatively uniform (900-1000 °C), after a certain time (about 40 min) the temperatures stabilized in the range from 800 °C to 1400 °C. Higher temperatures correspond to the parts at the top of the reactor, near the plasma source and low temperatures are near the bottom of the reactor. T1 was positioned near the exhaust for gas and solid particle products. From OP3 to OP8, marking the end of the experiment, T1 remained almost stable, with temperatures ranging between 1350-1400 °C. This suggests that the initial feeding of PP granules did not decompose completely at the beginning and required time for the feeding material, temperature, and output gas to reach stable conditions.

Figure 3. Temperature evolution in the reactor during experiment. Position of thermocouples corresponds to the schematic in Figure 1.

Following the feeding of plastics, the observed temperature increase indicates partial oxidation of the PP polymer, which is likely an exothermic phenomenon. The excess heat produced can facilitate the decomposition of the remaining material, primarily through pyrolysis at higher temperatures. As the process also produces solid carbon, it is a combination of gasification and pyrolysis.

The calibration of the output syngas depends primarily on the airflow rate introduced into the microwave plasma. During three specific conditions, OP3, OP6, and OP8, extra argon was fed into the reactor to cross-check the validity of the output gas calculations. Additionally, at OP7 and OP8, extra CO₂ was introduced to the reactor to investigate its decomposition into CO and oxygen atoms and to evaluate its utilization based on the Boudouard reaction.

The online gas composition analysis of the produced syngas measured by mass spectrometer is presented in **Figure 4**. At the beginning of the process, during the initial feeding stage, fluctuations in the feed caused the oxygen levels to vary. However, once the oxygen completely reacted with the PP polymers, no oxygen remained in the reactor. The online gas composition was measured using a mass spectrometer. Due to the overlapping atomic weights of nitrogen and carbon monoxide, these gases appear as a single line. To differentiate between them, FTIR gas analysis was applied. The final gas compositions under various operating conditions are shown in **Figure 5**.

Under OPs, OP1 and OP2, the hydrogen concentrations were 0.2% and 1.4%, respectively, while the carbon monoxide concentrations were 2.1% and 3.4%, respectively. At the start of the feeding process, it took approximately 30 minutes to stabilize the gasification process. During this initial stage, the system exhibited combustion-like conditions rather than gasification. This combustion, being exothermic, caused the reactor exhaust gas temperature to rise to 1400 °C. After stabilization, the hydrogen and carbon monoxide concentrations remained consistent.

For OP3 to OP6, the hydrogen concentrations were 16.5%, 17.2%, 18.6%, and 15.1%, respectively. For OP3 and OP4, the PP feeding rate was 15 kg/h, with hydrogen concentration higher in OP4 due to the addition of argon in OP3. For OP5 and OP6, the PP feeding rate increased to 18 kg/h, and argon was again added in OP6 to calibrate the gas composition.

In OP7 and OP8, 46 SLM (standard liters per minute) of carbon dioxide was fed into the system to evaluate the gasification rate and investigate whether the additional carbon dioxide would enhance the gasification process. The results showed an increase in hydrogen and carbon monoxide concentrations to 19.7% and 17.6%, respectively, the highest observed levels. This confirms that the addition of carbon dioxide boosts the gasification rate.

Figure 4. Composition analysis of produced gases during the experiment, showing volume % of each gas. Data derived from combined mass spectrometry and FTIR analysis.

Figure 5. Produced Syngas composition in different operation conditions

3.2. Characterization of the carbon nanomaterial

Although the process primarily involved the gasification of PP, the higher carbon-to-oxygen ratio resulted in incomplete gasification. As a result, some of the carbon underwent pyrolysis instead, releasing hydrogen and forming solid carbon nanoparticles. These nanoparticles were carried out of the reactor along with the produced syngas. Upon cooling, the solid particles separated from the syngas and were collected using a filtration system. The resulting solid carbon was analyzed and characterized using various techniques, including STEM, TEM, BET, laser diffraction particle size analysis, XRD, and Raman spectroscopy.

Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM)

STEM images, including bright field (BF), dark field (DF), and high-angle annular dark field

(HAADF), are presented in

Figure 6. These images reveal spherical carbon nanoparticles that, by clustering together, form carbon black agglomerates.

A comparison of images from three different sensors and positions reveals variations in the arrangement of carbon black agglomerates. In some areas, individual spherical carbon particles are connected in a chain-like structure, while in others, the particles form three-dimensional bulk accumulations. However, dark field (DF) and high-angle annular dark field (HAADF) imaging confirm that even in the densely accumulated 3D regions, the particles retain their spherical shape. This indicates uniformity in the morphology of the carbon nanoparticles, with all particles being spherical.

Figure 6. STEM Images of an agglomerated cluster of carbon nanoparticles, (a) Bright field, (b) Dark field and (c) HAADF

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

Produced carbon is also mostly spherical, ranging from 10 to 600 nm in diameter, and stuck together in irregular agglomerates (**Figure 7**). The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns show diffuse rings (**Figure 7.d**), typical for amorphous materials. The rings are situated in distances of 2.82, 4.84, and 8.25 nm⁻¹; this corresponds to interatomic distances of ~0.35, 0.20, and ~0.12 nm. The rings R2 and R3 are observed for all amorphous carbon materials, and the ring R1 corresponds to the spacings of nano-onion shells [42]. The spacing of 0.35 nm is close to that of basal planes in graphite (graphite layers spacing is 0.335 nm, and the spacing of C atoms is 0.142 nm). The result of the STEM-EDS analysis confirmed presence of carbon and traces of oxygen (**Figure 8**).

Figure 7. a., b., c. Bright-field TEM micrographs of carbon nanomaterials, d. SAED patterns of carbon nanomaterials

Figure 1. STEM bright-field micrograph of carbon, maps of C and O, and corresponding EDS spectrum.

BET and pore volume analysis

The isotherm gas adsorption and desorption of produced carbon are shown at **Figure 9**. The isotherm exhibits a Type IV curve, characteristic of mesoporous materials with pore sizes between 2-50 nm. The hysteresis loop between the adsorption and desorption curves indicates capillary condensation within the mesopores, suggesting pores with cylindrical geometries. At low pressures ($P/P_0 < 0.1$), adsorption is gradual, indicating monolayer adsorption on the surface, while at higher pressures ($P/P_0 > 0.4$), adsorption increases sharply due to multilayer adsorption and capillary condensation, confirmed by the pronounced hysteresis loop from $P/P_0 = 0.5$ to 0.95.

The material's BET surface area is $29.43 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, indicating a relatively large surface area suitable for adsorption applications. A pore size distribution graph from DFT analysis shows that most pores are around 5 nm, with a secondary peak at 7-10 nm, confirming a bimodal distribution. The total pore volume is $0.0493 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$, and while the majority of the pores are in the 2-6 nm range, there are also larger pores up to 10-12 nm.

Overall, the material is mesoporous, with primary pore sizes between 2-10 nm, making it suitable for applications like catalysis, adsorption, or filtration due to its significant surface area and well-defined pore structure.

Figure 9. Nitrogen adsorption/Desorption isotherm (a) and pore size distribution calculated by DFT method (b)

Laser diffraction – particle size analysis

The particle size distribution is shown in **Figure 10**. follows a normal distribution ranging from 250 nm to 7.2 μm , with the peak volume density indicating a particle size of 1.5 μm , corresponding to carbon agglomerates. Additionally, there is a minor tail, representing smaller particles around 150 nm and larger particles extending to 12 μm .

It is important to note that this size distribution corresponds to carbon particle agglomerates rather than individual particles. This indicates that individual carbon spherical particles are chemically attached, forming agglomerates. These agglomerates behave as single entities and cannot be easily separated into individual particles, even when suspended in a solvent. If separation is achieved, the particles rapidly re-agglomerate due to strong physical forces of attraction.

Figure 10. Particle size distribution by volume density (%) and cumulative volume density (%)

Raman Spectroscopy

The Raman spectroscopy analysis of the carbon produced by microwave plasma gasification of polypropylene (PP) is shown in **Figure 11**. The deconvolution reveals four peaks at 1355, 1586, 2660, and 2936 cm^{-1} , which correspond to the D1, G, 2*D1, and G+D1 peaks, respectively. Detailed information on deconvolution is shown in **Table 2**. We used Lorentz fitting because many studies assume it [34][35][36]. Based on Knight's empirical formula [37] with the I_D/I_G ratio of 0.90, the calculated L_a is 4.88 nm, which corresponds to the size of the carbon nanocrystalline plates.

Table 2. Deconvolution information generated by Origin 2022b and used Lorentz fitting

Model	Lorentz			
Equation	$y = y_0 + (2*A/\pi) * (w/(4*(x-xc)^2 + w^2))$			
Plot	Peak1(D1)	Peak2(G)	Peak3(2*D1)	Peak4(G+D1)
Offset (y0)	120.66837 ± 1.13661	120.66837 ± 1.13661	120.66837 ± 1.13661	120.66837 ± 1.13661
Peak Center(xc)	1355.20495 ± 0.5742	1586.43827 ± 0.3242	2660.82428 ± 12.67221	2936.33545 ± 19.29993
FWHM (W)	232.9016 ± 2.05782	90.18481 ± 1.10132	410.76445 ± 29.34113	464.66574 ± 37.60691
Area (A)	249304.83319 ± 1970.6642	93495.49156 ± 1008.7782	63271.62084 ± 9314.46333	57624.10247 ± 9704.29015
Reduced Chi-Sqr	663.96964			
R-Square (COD)	0.97771			
Adj. R-Square	0.97762			

Figure 11. Raman spectrum of produced carbon, which was determined using 532 nm laser, includes the deconvolution to identify the G and D1 and 2D and G+D1 peaks

3.3. Characterization of prepared carbides

The prepared carbon nanomaterials were utilized as precursors for the targeted synthesis of TiC carbides via short-term high-energy mechanical alloying (MA). XRD analysis revealed distinct behaviors in the powder mixtures, with a 1:1 atomic ratio of Ti:C being more effective to TiC formation (see **Table 3**). Notably, just 2 h of MA process resulted in 7 wt.% TiC for the 1:1 mixture. Extending the alloying duration to 4 h significantly increased the TiC content to 68 wt.% for the 1:1 mixture, whereas the 1:2 mixture yielded only 11 wt.% TiC under identical conditions. Achieving 68 wt.% TiC within 4 h of MA is remarkable, considering the typically much longer durations of mechanical alloying reported by others.

The conventional preparation of TiC often involves mechanical alloying of TiO₂ with carbon for extended periods, depending on the specific MA setup [38][39][40][41][42][43]. However, even such prolonged processes rarely result in complete transformation of TiO₂ into TiC or its formation from pure elemental precursors. Interestingly, the use of asphalt as a non-conventional carbon source has yielded fully transformed TiC, albeit also requiring up to 45 h of mechanical alloying [39]. Mechanical alloying is known to enhance reaction rates by altering diffusion pathways through induced lattice stress-strain and varying the powder-to-ball weight ratio [44][45].

Extending the mechanical alloying duration to 6 h induced pyrophoric behavior in both the systems, with spontaneous ignition occurring upon opening the cooled-down jar. This altered the phase composition, producing a mixture of Ti, TiC, and TiO_x phases, with TiO_x reaching up to 22 wt.% as is shown in XRD spectrums (**Figure 12**). Further extending the duration to 8 h did not increase TiC content; however, it led to finer powder particles, exacerbating their pyrophoric nature and raising TiO_x content to 26 wt.%.

The highest TiC content of 70 wt.% was achieved after 6 h of MA in the 1:1 mixture. Beyond this point, continued particle refinement promoted pyrophoric behavior, causing a decline in TiC content and an increase in TiO_x formation. In contrast, the 1:2 mixture stabilized at a TiO_x content of 22 wt.% after igniting at 6h of MA process. The differences in maximum TiO_x content between the two mixtures can be attributed to the varying carbon content. Carbon's presence facilitated partial reduction of the newly formed TiO_x during combustion. This hypothesis is supported by the observation that the 1:2 powder mixture retained approximately 1 wt.% carbon even after 8 h of MA.

Similar ignition phenomena have been documented in the literature [40][46], where carbon diffusion along Ti grain boundaries resulted in the formation of a transitional Ti-C bonded state. This occurred due to shifts in binding energies between C 1s and Ti 2p electrons [40], significantly lowering the energy barrier for self-combustion. In our study, intensive microstructural refinement similarly reduced the diffusion path length between Ti and C at their boundaries [40]. Under an inert atmosphere, this led to self-ignition upon opening the jar. Moreover, the presence of n-heptane may have contributed to this behavior. Volatile organic compounds can promote gaseous interactions at the powder-ball-wall interface, one of the three recognized diffusion-related mechanisms [47], further enhancing carbon diffusion to Ti boundaries.

Table 3. Phase composition (wt.%) of the prepared powder mixtures as a result of MA duration.

Powder mixture	Duration of MA (h)	Phase composition (wt.%)				
		Ti	C	TiC	TiO _x	Fe
1:1, 4 wt.% n-heptane	as-mixed	95	5	-	-	-
	2	93	-	7	-	-
	4	30	-	68	1	1
	6	12	-	70	17	1
	8	9	-	64	26	1
1:2, 4 wt.% n-heptane	as-mixed	93	7	-	-	-
	2	93	2	5	-	-
	4	88	1	11	-	-
	6	52	1	25	22	-
	8	52	1	89	23	-

Figure 12: XRD diffraction patterns of the mechanically alloyed Ti-C systems showing the phases' formation kinetics within the: a) 1:1 atomic ratio of Ti:C; b) 1:2 atomic ratio of Ti:C powder mixtures.

4. Conclusions

High power microwave plasma gasification was conducted to gasify polypropylene (PP), with plasma power set to 20 kW and 40 kW, and oxygen from air serving as the oxidation agent. Initially, after feeding the PP, the process was primarily combustion, with minimal hydrogen and CO production. However, this combustion phase elevated the reactor temperature to 1400 °C, which subsequently led to the production of hydrogen and CO, while the CO₂ levels decreased significantly. The highest hydrogen production occurred at operating point OP7, where hydrogen made up 19.7% of the produced gas composition, corresponding to 271 SLM of hydrogen.

Throughout the process, carbon particles were produced due to incomplete gasification and excessively high temperatures. As a result, nearly pure carbon was formed with trace amounts of oxygen. The produced carbon was characterized as typical carbon black, featuring spherical nanoparticles and micrometer-scale agglomerations. The nanostructured carbon material was further tested to be use as a precursor for the targeted synthesis of carbides through short-term mechanical alloying (MA). The material's favorable properties facilitated the rapid formation of carbides, with initial traces of TiC appearing after just 2 h of MA. As the MA duration increased, the TiC content steadily grew. However, after 6 h of MA, spontaneous self-ignition occurred upon opening the milling jar, altering the phase composition of the powder mixture. This reaction led to the formation of TiO_x phases, which constituted up to 26 wt.%. Despite this challenge, the process demonstrates significant advantages. It leverages waste carbon by-products for efficient and rapid transformation into carbides, aligning with the principles of the circular economy. Furthermore, these carbides hold substantial potential for enhancing high-performance materials when used as reinforcement additives.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jafar Fathi: Conceptualization, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Michal Hlína:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Tomáš Mates:** Methodology Project administration. **Maksym Buryi:** Methodology. **Vineet Singh Sikarwar:** Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Radek Mušálek:** Formal analysis. **Shelja Sharma:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Michal Lojka:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Adéla Jiříčková:** Investigation. **Ondřej Jankovský:** Investigation, Funding aquisition, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Jan Riedl:** Data curation. **Miroslav Karlík:** Writing –

original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Petr Kratochvíl:** Investigation. **Hana Thürlová:** Investigation. **František Růžička:** Investigation. **Filip Průša:** Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Investigation. **Alan Mašláni:** Investigation, Project administration, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Acknowledgment

J. Fathi would like to thank ÚFP – MSCA Fellowships CZ project (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_010/0003322), which was co-funded by the EU and Czech Republic Ministry of Education. The authors would like to thank the Czech Science Foundation (project No. 24-10767S) for its financial support of this research. This publication was supported by the project "The Energy Conversion and Storage", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research. We would like to thank the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic (project No. TN02000069 National Centre of Competence MATCA) for the financial support of this research. We acknowledge CzechNanoLab Research Infrastructure supported by MEYS CR (project No. LM2023051). V. Sikarwar gratefully acknowledges the support from the Czech Academy of Sciences (Programme to Support Prospective Human Resources; Project L100432402). J. Fathi would also like to thank the Specific University Research Grant (A2_FC HT_2024_084).

Data statement

According to Open Science principles, raw data can be found at DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14468531

References

- [1] S. S. V. Vuppaladadiyam, A. K. Vuppaladadiyam, A. Sahoo, A. Urgunde, S. Murugavelh, V. Šrámek, *et al.*, "Waste to energy: Trending key challenges and current technologies in waste plastic management," *Sci. Total Environ.*, vol. 913, no. November 2023, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.169436.

- [2] A. Jemec Kokalj, A. Dolar, D. Drobne, M. Marinšek, M. Dolenc, L. Škrlep, *et al.*, “Environmental hazard of polypropylene microplastics from disposable medical masks: acute toxicity towards *Daphnia magna* and current knowledge on other polypropylene microplastics,” *Microplastics and Nanoplastics*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2022, doi: 10.1186/s43591-021-00020-0.
- [3] Y. Lian, R. Shi, J. Liu, A. Zeb, Q. Wang, J. Wang, *et al.*, “Effects of polystyrene, polyethylene, and polypropylene microplastics on the soil-rhizosphere-plant system: Phytotoxicity, enzyme activity, and microbial community,” *J. Hazard. Mater.*, vol. 465, no. 38, p. 133417, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2023.133417.
- [4] M. Kiehadrouinezhad, A. Merabet, and H. Hosseinzadeh-Bandbafha, “Landfill source of greenhouse gas emission,” *Adv. Technol. Dev. Greenh. Gases Emiss. Capture Convers. Greenh. Gases Emiss. Clim. Chang.*, pp. 123–145, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-443-19231-9.00023-5.
- [5] N. Yang, H. Zhang, M. Chen, L. M. Shao, and P. J. He, “Greenhouse gas emissions from MSW incineration in China: Impacts of waste characteristics and energy recovery,” *Waste Manag.*, vol. 32, no. 12, pp. 2552–2560, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2012.06.008.
- [6] K. L. Hwang, S. M. Choi, M. K. Kim, J. B. Heo, and K. D. Zoh, “Emission of greenhouse gases from waste incineration in Korea,” *J. Environ. Manage.*, vol. 196, pp. 710–718, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.03.071.
- [7] N. Singh and T. R. Walker, “Plastic recycling: A panacea or environmental pollution problem,” *npj Mater. Sustain.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–7, 2024, doi: 10.1038/s44296-024-00024-w.
- [8] N. Bahlouli, D. Pessey, C. Raveyre, J. Guillet, S. Ahzi, A. Dahoun, *et al.*, “Recycling effects on the rheological and thermomechanical properties of polypropylene-based composites,” *Mater. Des.*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 451–458, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2011.04.049.
- [9] M. G. Davidson, R. A. Furlong, and M. C. McManus, “Developments in the life cycle assessment of chemical recycling of plastic waste – A review,” *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 293, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126163.
- [10] J. Fathi, A. Mašláni, M. Hlína, F. Lukáč, R. Mušálek, O. Jankovský, *et al.*, “Multiple benefits of polypropylene plasma gasification to consolidate plastic treatment, CO₂ utilization, and renewable electricity storage,” *Fuel*, vol. 368, no. April, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.fuel.2024.131692.
- [11] A. Rida Galaly, G. Van Oost, and N. Dawood, “Sustainable Plasma Gasification Treatment of Plastic Waste: Evaluating Environmental, Economic, and Strategic Dimensions,” *ACS Omega*, vol. 9, no. 19, pp. 21174–21186, 2024, doi: 10.1021/acsomega.4c01084.
- [12] L. Dai, O. Karakas, Y. Cheng, K. Cobb, P. Chen, and R. Ruan, “A review on carbon materials production from plastic wastes,” *Chem. Eng. J.*, vol. 453, no. October 2022, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.cej.2022.139725.
- [13] A. Jiříčková, A.-M. Lauermannová, O. Jankovský, J. Fathi, M. Záleská, A. Pivák, *et al.*, “Utilization of waste carbon spheres in magnesium oxychloride cement,” *Case Stud. Constr. Mater.*, vol. 19, no. July, p. e02374, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.cscm.2023.e02374.
- [14] V. S. Sikarwar, A. Reichert, M. Pohorely, E. Meers, N. L. Ferreira, and M. Jeremias, “Equilibrium modeling of thermal plasma assisted co-valorization of difficult waste streams for syngas production,” *Sustain. Energy Fuels*, vol. 5, no. 18, pp. 4650–4660, 2021, doi: 10.1039/d1se00998b.

- [15] V. S. Sikarwar, N. R. Peela, A. K. Vuppaladadiyam, N. L. Ferreira, A. Mašláni, R. Tomar, *et al.*, “Thermal plasma gasification of organic waste stream coupled with CO₂-sorption enhanced reforming employing different sorbents for enhanced hydrogen production,” *RSC Adv.*, vol. 12, no. 10, pp. 6122–6132, 2022, doi: 10.1039/d1ra07719h.
- [16] V. S. Sikarwar, A. Mašláni, G. Van Oost, J. Fathi, M. Hlína, T. Mates, *et al.*, “Integration of thermal plasma with CCUS to valorize sewage sludge,” *Energy*, vol. 288, no. September 2023, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2023.129896.
- [17] V. S. Sikarwar, A. Masláni, M. Hlína, J. Fathi, T. Mates, M. Pohorelý, *et al.*, “Thermal plasma assisted pyrolysis and gasification of RDF by utilizing sequestered CO₂ as gasifying agent,” *J. CO₂ Util.*, vol. 66, no. October, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jcou.2022.102275.
- [18] S. Mohsenian, M. S. Esmaili, J. Fathi, and B. Shokri, “Hydrogen and carbon black nano-spheres production via thermal plasma pyrolysis of polymers,” *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 41, no. 38, pp. 16656–16663, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2016.05.150.
- [19] S. Mohsenian, M. S. Esmaili, J. Fathi, and B. Shokri, “Synthesis of carbon nano-spheres and nano-tubes by thermal plasma processing of polypropylene,” *Appl. Phys. A Mater. Sci. Process.*, vol. 124, no. 8, pp. 1–6, 2018, doi: 10.1007/s00339-018-1983-9.
- [20] P. Zhang, C. Liang, M. Wu, Y. Li, X. Chen, D. Liu, *et al.*, “Sustainable microwave-driven CO₂ gasification of plastic waste for high-yield H₂ and CO production,” *Appl. Catal. B Environ. Energy*, vol. 345, p. 123718, May 2024, doi: 10.1016/J.APCATB.2024.123718.
- [21] P. Zhang, C. Liang, M. Wu, X. Chen, D. Liu, and J. Ma, “High-efficient microwave plasma discharging initiated conversion of waste plastics into hydrogen and carbon nanotubes,” *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 268, p. 116017, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2022.116017.
- [22] Y. Cui, H. Shi, Y. Zhang, L. Cui, W. Zhao, and W. Liu, “Experimental Investigation on Air Gasification of Polypropylene Particles in a Microwave Fluidized Bed Reactor,” *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, vol. 62, no. 42, pp. 17306–17313, 2023, doi: 10.1021/acs.iecr.3c01136.
- [23] P. E. Ganza and B. J. Lee, “A novel method for industrial production of clean hydrogen (H₂) from mixed plastic waste,” *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 48, no. 40, pp. 15037–15052, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.01.010.
- [24] O. Akande, B. J. Lee, J. A. Okolie, and H. N. Museba, “Hydrogen-rich syngas generation through microwave plasma reforming of greenhouse gases,” *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 48, no. 89, pp. 34649–34658, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.05.262.
- [25] S. V. Meschel and O. J. Kleppa, “Thermochemistry of alloys of transition metals and lanthanide metals with some IIIB and IVB elements in the periodic table,” *J. Alloys Compd.*, vol. 321, no. 2, pp. 183–200, 2001, doi: 10.1016/S0925-8388(01)00966-5.
- [26] R.G. Coltters, “Thermodynamics of binary metallic carbides: A review,” *Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 76, Page 1-50, 1985, doi.org/10.1016/0025-5416(85)90078-3
- [27] W. Lengauer, “Transition Metal Carbides, Nitrides, and Carbonitrides,” *Handb. Ceram. Hard Mater.*, pp. 202–252, 2000, doi: 10.1002/9783527618217.ch7.
- [28] H. Mao, F. Shen, Y. Zhang, J. Wang, K. Cui, H. Wang, *et al.*, “Ceramics : A Review,” *Coatings*, vol. 11, no. 12, p. 1444, 2021.

- [29] S.T. OYAMA, "The Chemistry of Transition Metal Carbides and Nitrides", *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 1, Page 1-14,
- [30] H. Liu, J. Zhu, Y. Liu, and Z. Lai, "First-principles study on the mechanical properties of vanadium carbides VC and V₄C₃," *Mater. Lett.*, vol. 62, no. 17–18, pp. 3084–3086, 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.matlet.2008.01.136.
- [31] M. S. El-Eskandarany, "Synthesis of nanocrystalline titanium carbide alloy powders by mechanical solid state reaction," *Metall. Mater. Trans. A Phys. Metall. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 27, no. 8, pp. 2374–2382, 1996, doi: 10.1007/BF02651892.
- [32] X. Zhu, K. Zhao, B. Cheng, Q. Lin, X. Zhang, T. Chen, *et al.*, "Synthesis of nanocrystalline TiC powder by mechanical alloying," *Mater. Sci. Eng. C*, vol. 16, no. 1–2, pp. 103–105, 2001, doi: 10.1016/S0928-4931(01)00283-1.
- [33] S. Huang, H. Wu, H. Zhu, Z. Xie, and J. Cheng, "Enhanced tensile properties of CrMnFeCoNi_{0.8} high entropy alloy with in-situ TiC particles," *Intermetallics*, vol. 148, no. November 2021, pp. 1–7, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.intermet.2022.107639.
- [34] S. Vol and I. Suppl, "Pergamon SOOT CHARACTERIZATION IN ATMOSPHERIC PARTICLES F R O M," vol. 30, pp. 907–908, 1999.
- [35] R. E. View, "1979 of J.," *Carbon N. Y.*, vol. 20, no. 2, 1979.
- [36] B. Dippel, H. Jander, and J. Heintzenberg, "NIR FT Raman spectroscopic study of flame soot," *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, vol. 1, no. 20, pp. 4707–4712, 1999, doi: 10.1039/a904529e.
- [37] TUINSTRA F and KOENIG JL, "Raman Spectrum of Graphite," *J. Chem. Phys.*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 1126–1130, 1970, doi: 10.1063/1.1674108.
- [38] H. E. J. Suárez, N. A. de Sanchez, and J. A. A. Diaz, "Titanium Carbide (TiC) Production by Mechanical Alloying," *Powder Technol.*, 2018, doi: 10.5772/intechopen.76690.
- [39] B. Li, L. Cui, Y. Zheng, and C. Xu, "Synthesis of TiC Powder by Mechanical Alloying of Titanium and Asphalt," *Chinese J. Chem. Eng.*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 138–140, 2007, doi: 10.1016/S1004-9541(07)60047-0.
- [40] N. Q. Wu, S. Lin, J. M. Wu, Z. Z. Li, S. Lin, J. M. Wu, *et al.*, "Mechanosynthesis mechanism of TiC powders Mechanosynthesis Mechanism of TiC powders," vol. 0836, no. March, 2016.
- [41] W. M. Tang, Z. X. Zheng, W. C. Wu, J. Lü, J. W. Liu, and J. M. Wang, "Structural evolutions of mechanically alloyed and heat treated Ti₅₀C₅₀ and Ti₃₃B₆₇ powders," *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, vol. 99, no. 1, pp. 144–149, 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.matchemphys.2005.09.085.
- [42] M. Razavi, M. R. Rahimipour, and A. H. Rajabi-Zamani, "Synthesis of nanocrystalline TiC powder from impure Ti chips via mechanical alloying," *J. Alloys Compd.*, vol. 436, no. 1–2, pp. 142–145, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2006.07.018.
- [43] B. H. Lohse, A. Calka, and D. Wexler, "Effect of starting composition on the synthesis of nanocrystalline TiC during milling of titanium and carbon," *J. Alloys Compd.*, vol. 394, no. 1–2, pp. 148–151, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2004.09.074.
- [44] J. S. Forrester and G. B. Schaffer, "The chemical kinetics of mechanical alloying," *Metall. Mater. Trans. A*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 725–730, 1995, doi: 10.1007/BF02663921.

- [45] B. J. M. Aikin, T. H. Courtney, and D. R. Maurice, "Reaction rates during mechanical alloying," *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 147, no. 2, pp. 229–237, 1991, doi: 10.1016/0921-5093(91)90850-M.
- [46] Z. G. Liu, J. T. Guo, L. L. Ye, G. S. Li, and Z. Q. Hu, "Formation mechanism of TiC by mechanical alloying," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 65, no. 21, pp. 2666–2668, 1994, doi: 10.1063/1.112596.
- [47] L. Lu and M. Lai, "of New Materials By Mechanical Alloying," vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 33–39, 1995.

Abbreviations

Polypropylene ----- PP

Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy---- STEM

Transmission Electron Microscopy--- TEM

Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy---- EDS

Brunauer-Emmett-Teller theory---- BET

X-ray Diffraction----XRD

Density Functional Theory--- DFT

selected area electron diffraction---- SAED

laser diffraction particle size distribution----- LD

High-Angle Annular Dark Field----- HAADF

Bright Field----- BF

Dark Field----- DF

Standard liter per minute---- SLM